

In Human and Veterinary Medicine: The Golden Age of Antibiotics is Coming to an End- Case of *Staphylococcus aureus*

Dr. Rachid Hnini

Biological Engineering Laboratory, Pathology and Functional Biology Team, Sultan Moulay Slimane University, FST, PO.Box: 523, 23000 Beni Mellal, Morocco.

Received: May 11, 2025

Accepted: Jun 10, 2025

Published: Jun 18, 2025

ABSTRACT_ By 2050, without joint international action, antibiotic resistance could become one of the leading causes of mortality worldwide, causing up to 10 million deaths each year. It is in this context that the World Health Organization (WHO) has identified antibiotic resistance as one of the most serious threats to global public health. In addition to death and disability, antimicrobial resistance has significant economic costs. The World Bank estimates that antimicrobial resistance could result in US\$ 1 trillion additional healthcare costs by 2050, and US\$ 1 trillion to US\$ 3.4 trillion gross domestic product (GDP) losses per year by 2030. Worldly, *Staphylococcus aureus* is well-known to be among various pathogenic gram-positive bacteria and it stand out as being responsible for global resistance challenges, significant public health burden, and cost to healthcare. In human as in animal health, *Staphylococcus aureus* can result in a wide range of diseases, including osteomyelitis, endocarditis, mastitis, thrombophlebitis, meningitis, skin and soft tissue infections, surgical and trauma wound infections, urinary tract infections, gastrointestinal tract infections, pneumonia, toxic shock syndrome, septicaemia, and infections of indwelling medical devices. Earlier, most infections caused by Staphylococcae species can be easily treated with antibiotics; however, in recent years *Staphylococcus* found its manner to resist the commonly used and effective antibiotics. Nowadays, scientists have warned that the world, in few coming years, will return to a pre-antibiotic age plagued by life-threatening microbial infections on the basis of a recent antibiotic resistance gene database that lists the existence of more than 20,000 antibiotic-resistant genes of 400 types, predicted from available genome sequences. As a consequence of this new challenge, the discovery of novel antimicrobial agents to which microbes cannot develop resistance easily is one of the major medical concerns of the 21st century.

Key words: Human and veterinary medicine, Antibiotic resistance, *Staphylococcus aureus*, genes, World Health Organization.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Rachid Hnini

In human and veterinary medicine, antimicrobial agents play an important role in the therapy of bacterial infections [1,2]. However, the resistance problem that human and animal health encountered often after use of these antimicrobial agents against these bacterial infections manifest, often quickly, after each introduction of new classes of antimicrobial drugs [3]. The discovery of antimicrobial agents during the 20th century has been considered one of the wonder discoveries [4], but the increase of antimicrobials resistance encountered in hospitals, communities, and the environment concomitant with their utilization also increased [2,4]. Antimicrobials are classically defined as substances that destroy or inhibit the growth of pathogenic groups of microorganisms, including bacteria, viruses, protozoa, and fungi, while antibiotics are defined as substances (not limited to those produced from micro-organisms) that can kill or inhibit the growth of bacteria [5]. Microorganisms remained as one of the most important production sources of new bioactive substances including antibiotics, immunosuppressants, anti-parasitics, anti-tumor, hypocholesterolemic agents, and enzyme inhibitors [6-8]. In human and veterinary medicine, antibacterials remain the most important drugs administered [2,9]. According to authors, the classifications of antibacterial are based on their mechanism of action, chemical structure, and spectrum of activity or source. The most important antibacterial classes are Beta-lactams (Cephalosporins and Penicillins), Aminoglycosides, Macrolides, Lincosamides, Amphenicols, Nitrofurans, Quinolones, Sulfonamides, Tetracyclines, and Miscellaneous [9]. Beta-lactam antibiotics family, such as penicillin compounds, continues to be one of the most frequently used drugs in veterinary and human medicine [10]. Indeed, Beta lactams have been the most widely used antibiotics drugs for more than eight decades and still constitute the most important group of antibiotics described in medicine. They are divided into two subcategories: Penicillins and Cephalosporins. In general, Beta-lactam family is used as growth promoters, and chemotherapeutic and/or prophylactic agents; but, their extensive utilization in veterinary medicine practices causes numerous residues in foodstuffs, which present a serious health hazard, mainly regarding the development of resistance in target organisms [11]. In addition to this antimicrobials family, the discovery of Aminoglycosides compounds also introduced a new therapeutic concept in medicine, especially after the discovery and emergence of the first penicillin resistant strains after the introduction of this antibiotic for the first time in 1940, what constitutes a new challenger that has really started to threat human and animal health. In 1943, the discovery by Selman Waksman and his student, Albert Schatz, of streptomycin, a natural antibiotic molecule produced by *Streptomyces griseus* [12], caused great excitement in the medical community as it proved to be the first clinical treatment against tuberculosis. This earned Waksman the Nobel Prize for Medicine in 1952. In the years following this momentous success, many similar compounds, such as neomycin or kanamycin, were isolated from bacterial strains of the family Actinomycetes [13]. Aminoglycosides compounds family are antibacterials with broad-spectrum isolated from *Streptomyces* and *Micromonospora* bacteria. This antibiotics family compounds are characterized by two or more amino sugars linked by glycosidic bonds to an aminocyclitol component [14], and they are administered both therapeutically and prophylactically to treat cattle, swine, and poultry [9]. In the literature, Macrolides were the third major class of microbial products to be discovered that possess antibiotic properties after Beta-lactams and Aminoglycosides [15]. Macrolides are antibiotic compounds composed of 14 (erythromycin and clarithromycin), 15 (azithromycin), or 16 (josamycin, spiramycin, tylosin)-membered lactones to which amino and/or neutral sugars are linked [16-18]. The archetypal Macrolide, erythromycin, was the first antibiotic compound isolated from the soil dwelling bacterium *Saccharopolyspora erythrea* in 1949 in a Filipino environmental sample [19]. Three years later, this Macrolide antibiotic entered clinical practice, exactly in 1952. According to Golkar *et al.* [19], this kick-started the golden age of Macrolide discovery where a plethora of new Macrolides were being frequently characterized.

What is more interesting, this marvelous discovery fueled the development of next-generation Macrolides using semi-synthetic approaches [20]. In general, Macrolide antibiotics have been used and described in both agriculture and medicine [19]. Furthermore, Macrolides such as erythromycin and azithromycin have found use as substitutes for Beta-lactam antibiotics in patients with penicillin allergies [19,21]. In the world, azithromycin remains among the most successful and highly prescribed antibiotics [22]. In medicine, the great neediness for an alternative treatment to penicillin-allergic patients has increased the clinical application of Macrolides worldwide [19]. Furthermore, Macrolide, Lincosamide and Streptogramin B (MLSB) antibiotics stay one of the available options for treating infections caused by *Staphylococcaceae* germs [23]. Action mode of MLSB antibiotics are similar because they inhibit synthesis of protein by targeting the peptidyl transferase center within the 50S subunit (23s rRNA) of the bacterial ribosome [24]. In this context, the peptidyl transferase center is known as the main target site for many antibiotics, but the exact mechanism for its activity is still unclear [25]. Several studies suggested that MLSB could also inhibit peptidyl transferase by interfering with the proper positioning and movement of the tRNAs at the peptidyl transferase cavity [26-28]. The discovery of Tetracyclines was also in the 1940s, Tetracyclines are an antibiotics family that inhibits synthesis of protein by preventing the attachment of aminoacyl-tRNA to the ribosomal acceptor (A) site [29]. Otherwise, Tetracycline inhibits cell growth by binding to the 16S part of the 30S ribosomal subunit preventing aminoacyl Trna from binding to the ribosome A site. This leads to inhibition of translation hampering cell growth [30]. The wide use of Tetracyclines, in veterinary medicine, was for cost-effective prophylactic and therapeutic treatment and also as growth promoters in cattle and poultry [9]. Overall, Tetracyclines are broad-spectrum compounds, exhibiting activity against a large variety of gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria, atypical organisms such as chlamydiae, mycoplasmas, and rickettsiae, and protozoan parasites [29]. The favorable antimicrobial properties of Tetracyclines compounds and the absence of major adverse side effects have conducted to their widespread utilization in the therapy of human and animal infections [29]. Chloramphenicol is else an antibiotic with broad spectrum, it was originally isolated from culture filtrates of the fungus *Streptomyces venezuelae* [31-35] and subsequently was synthesized chemically [33,36]. Chloramphenicol acts by disrupting bacterial peptide bond formation by reversibly binding to the 50s subunit of the 70s ribosome, inhibiting the formation of bacterial ribosomes from soluble RNA [34,35]. On the whole, Aminoglycosides, Macrolides, Lincosamides, Streptogramins, Chloramphenicols and Tetracyclines families are antibiotics that act as protein synthesis inhibitors. However, and because of importance of exchange of intra- and extracellular substances that takes places through microbial cell membranes. Certain antimicrobials agents act as cell membrane function inhibitors such as Polymyxin, a group of antibiotics that is characterized by a cyclic peptide with a long hydrophobic tail [37]. Thus cell survival can be at stake if there is disruption of cell membrane structure because of leakage of important intercellular solutes. Cell membrane is found in both prokaryotic and eukaryotic organisms causing poor selectivity and thus compromising its use in the mammalian host, for example, Polymyxin [37]. In human medicine, the administration of synthetic peptides as therapeutics or diagnostics is well-established; but, a few of these drugs have also found use for comparable indications in veterinary. Peptide-based drugs are especially indicated for treating animals used in food production, though regulation of fertility is their most important application. In parallel to utilization of antibacterials originated from microorganisms, there are also introduction of synthetic antibacterial compounds such as Sulfonamides, Nitrofurans and Quinolones in treatment of several diseases infections caused by pathogenic germs. For example, Sulfonamides (sulphonamides) are a group of man-made (synthetic) medicines that contain the Sulfonamide chemical group. They are also known as Sulfa drugs name. The first Sulfonamide developed was sulfanilamide in 1906, but it was not

utilized as an antimicrobial compound until the late 1930s [38]. Sulfonamides have a broad-spectrum bacteriostatic (stop bacteria from reproducing but don't necessarily kill them) of antimicrobial activity against many microorganisms including bacteria and some protozoa, such as *Toxoplasma* and *Plasmodia* [39] and work by interfering with the synthesis of folic acid in bacteria, which is essential for nucleic acid formation and ultimately RNA and DNA [38]. Humans achieve folic acid from their diet, although bacteria need to synthesize it. Sulfonamide antimicrobials can be combined with trimethoprim to make them bactericidal, because trimethoprim acts on a different enzyme in the folic acid synthesis pathway [38]. The Nitrofurans antimicrobials like nifurtimox and furazolidone are known for their therapeutic value in the treatment of several illnesses, caused by protozoa or by certain gram-positive or gram-negative bacteria [37], such as trypanosomiasis, giardiasis and urinary tract infections in humans [40] and do not contribute to the development of antimicrobial resistance [37]. In the European Union, the use of Nitrofurans for livestock production was completely prohibited in 1995, due to concerns about the carcinogenicity of the drug residues and their potential harmful effects on human health [37,41]. However, Quinolones and Fluoroquinolones are known as a class of broad-spectrum antibiotics that are active against Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria [42]. For what is concerning their use nowadays in medicine, the European Medicines Agency's (EMA) Pharmacovigilance Risk Assessment Committee (PRAC) has recently recommended restricting the use of fluoroquinolone and quinolone antibiotics (described by mouth, injection or inhalation) following a review of disabling and potentially long-lasting side effects reported with these drugs. The review incorporated the views of patients, healthcare professionals and academics presented at EMA's public hearing on Fluoroquinolone and Quinolone antibiotics in June 2018 [42]. Except for the antibacterials belonging in the precedent groups, there are also several subgroups of antibacterials, such as Pleuromutilins, Diaminopyrimidines, Peptides, Quinoxalines, and Dapsone, which are widely used in meat producing animals. Pleuromutilins were discovered as natural-product antibiotics in 1950. However, the appearance of tiamulin as the first Pleuromutilin compound to be approved for veterinary use was in 1979, followed by valnemulin in 1999. Likewise; we must wait till 2007, date that retapamulin became the first Pleuromutilin approved for use in humans [43]. All antibiotics from Pleuromutilins class are generally known as compounds that selectively inhibit bacterial translation and are semisynthetic derivatives of the naturally occurring tricyclic diterpenoid pleuromutilin, which received its name from the pleuromutilin producing fungus *Pleurotus mutilus*. Tiamulin and valnemulin are two established derivatives in veterinary medicine for oral and intramuscular administration [44]. Concerning antibacterial Diaminopyrimidines class, it is well notorious that the value of the Sulfonamides as single antimicrobial agents has been greatly diminished both by their relatively low potency compared to more modern antimicrobial drugs on the one hand and by widespread acquired resistance on the one other hand. Conversely, when combined with antibacterial Diaminopyrimidines such as trimethoprim, resistance occurs less frequently and thus their usefulness has been enhanced [45]. Quinoxaline moiety is a part of various antibiotics such as echinomycin, levomycine, actinoleutine and also acts as antiviral, antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory, kinase inhibitors, anticancer, ion channel regulators and antiprotozoa agent. Although, Dapsone is a chemical class different from Sulfonamides but its mechanism of action is similar to Sulfonamides via inhibition of bacterial synthesis of dihydrofolic acid by competing with para-aminobenzoate for the active site of dihydropteroate synthase. There is no veterinary approved form of Dapsone. It is potentially useful for the oral treatment of some protozoal infections in horses. Dapsone class is carcinogenic and should be used with caution in pregnant and nursing animals. Nowadays, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, and enterococci are well-known to be among various pathogenic gram-positive bacteria and they stand out as being responsible for global resistance challenges, significant

public health burden, and cost to healthcare [46]. In human as in animal health, Gram-positive infections can result in a wide range of diseases, including osteomyelitis, endocarditis, mastitis, thrombophlebitis, meningitis, skin and soft tissue infections, surgical and trauma wound infections, urinary tract infections, gastrointestinal tract infections, pneumonia, toxic shock syndrome, septicemia, and infections of indwelling medical devices [47]. Earlier, most infections caused by *Staphylococcae* species can be easily treated with antibiotics; however, in recent years *Staphylococcus* found its manner to resist the commonly used and effective antibiotics; these antibiotics include Macrolides, Lincosamides, Streptogramins, Tetracyclines, Aminoglycosides (particularly gentamicin) and Beta-lactams (particularly methicillin) [48-51]. These antibiotics families are extensively used and more described in human and veterinary medicine especially for cost-effective prophylactic and therapeutic treatment and they are also used as growth promoters in cattle and poultry. However, their usefulness has been reduced with the onset of bacterial resistance [52]. For example, the large Tetracyclines description in veterinary medicine was used mainly for cost-effective prophylactic and therapeutic treatment and also as growth promoters in cattle and poultry [37]. The importance of antimicrobial therapy in dairy cow stays an imperative strategy for mastitis control as well as human infections [53].

Several infections, caused by staphylococcal or other agents, are recognized as an endemic disease and considered to be the most prevalent problem and expensive disease in veterinary and human medicine worldwide [2,54-56]. About 140 microorganisms species, have been recognized as etiological agents of humans and animals diseases [2,57], as *Klebsiella* spp., *P. aeruginosa*, *S. uberis*., *E. coli*, *S. agalactiae*, *Coagulase-Negative Staphylococci* and *Enterococcus* [58-60]. *S. aureus* is of particular importance, because it is highly infectious [61] and it is characterized by significantly lower cure levels in comparison with infections caused by other microorganisms [62]. Moreover, the *S. aureus* has the potential to expand evidence resistance to almost all the antimicrobial compounds classes [53] as a response to the selective pressure of antimicrobials, which will narrow the treatment options for veterinarians and clinicians [59,63].

Antimicrobials play critical roles in promoting human and animal health; however, their widespread use has placed a significant burden on antimicrobial resistance (AMR), posing a serious threat to public health [64-66]. Excessive antimicrobial use in animals has been extensively documented as a major contributing factor to AMR in animal, human and environmental sectors [67-69], which has become a worldwide concern and led to the development of global action plans against antimicrobial resistance [70]. According to Ibrahim *et al.* [71], worldwide utilization of antimicrobials in the production of food animals has been estimated at 63,151 (\pm 1560) tons in 2010 and it is estimated to increase by 67% to 105,596 (\pm 3605) tons by 2030. Two-thirds (66%) of global antimicrobial consumption growth (67%) is due to the increasing number of animals raised for food production. The remaining third (34%) is due to a shift in farming practices. It is expected that the larger section of animals to be raised by 2030 will be via intensive farming. By 2030, antimicrobial consumption in Asia is for example predicted to be 51,851 tons. It represents 82% of the current global consumption of antimicrobials in food animals in 2010. In herds, ~80.0% of these antimicrobials are only described for the treatment of bovine mastitis disease [72], as antibiotic therapy remains the primary choice for mastitis control in lactating and dry cows [73]. To note, the first antimicrobials usage in veterinary medicine was noted in dairy cows for treatment mastitis disease caused by *S. aureus* in addition to other pathogenic bacteria [74]. *S. aureus* is known as a bacterium that can employ galactose and lactose as energy sources, and as such is a notorious cause manifested in case of bovine and ovine mastitis [75,76] and food poisoning via contaminated food, dairy associated especially. Staphylococci are considered to be together with Streptococci members of a group of bacteria recognized as the invasive pyogenic cocci,

since they can cause a variety of suppurative or pus-forming diseases in humans and other animals [77]. Similar to other microorganisms, *S. aureus* uses a set of natural or acquired strategies and mechanisms to escape or avoid the direct action of host immune system. More than 90.0% of clinical *S. aureus* isolates elaborate polysaccharidic capsules, among which 11 serotypes have been showed [78,79]. According to authors, capsules type 5 and type 8 *S. aureus* have been encountered in up to 75.0% of clinical infections caused by this pathogenic bacterium. However, around of 20.0% of human isolates and up to 86.0% of bovine strains of *S. aureus* have been so far non-typable [80]. As well, the capsule protects the bacteria from phagocytosis. Lysozyme, is a muramidase enzyme that present in various host tissues such as mucous membranes, respiratory and intestinal tracts and also in fluids such as serum, saliva, and tears do not kill *S. aureus*. This resistance can contribute to its capacity to colonize skin and mucosal tissues, for example, the anterior nares [81]. Mechanisms of persistence of *S. aureus* in intra-mammary environments still need to be explored but evasion of host immune system and adherence to epithelial cells of mammary glands are some of the known in this regard [76]. For example, bovine mastitis, caused by staphylococcal or other agents, are recognized as an endemic disease and considered to be the most prevalent and expensive disease in the dairy farms, still remaining as an economically relevant problem to the dairy industry in several countries [54,55]. As example, the occurrence of mastitis pathogens and their antimicrobial resistance have been studied in numerous scientific investigations around the world [82]. Concerning the evolution of this resistance prevalence in the world, for example Erskineet *al.* [83] have concluded in a retrospective study on mastitis malady in Finland two times the reduction of *S. aureus* resistance against penicillin while six times resistance against erythromycin over a period of 6 years. According to Aqib *et al.* [84], this was not true because in reports encompassing findings of studies conducted in other geographical zones where resistance to the antibacterial drug increased to double of what was reported 12 years ago [85,86]. Later to 2001, the studies have indicated increase in general resistance of *S. aureus* strains against all antibiotics compounds. According to Aqib *et al.* [84], this difference observed in trends could be attributed to evolution of resistance against local microflora being under therapy selection, drug regulation of country, traditions of farmers, local antibiotic therapy protocols, and number of processed samples in the study. The main objectives of development of antibiotics drugs were definitively to fight against almost all pathogenic bacteria causing various infections and are now readily available worldly. According to Lewies *et al.* [87], the successful deployment of antibiotics has unfortunately resulted in these drugs being used more as a financial commodity rather than a valuable community resource that should be rationally managed. This has conducted to the accelerated development of antimicrobial resistance among many bacteria over the world [87]. However, the growing resistance noted to antibiotics drugs can be connected to antibiotic overuse and requires to be addressed promptly as previously reported by Netsvyetayeva *et al.* [88]. It appears from the literature reports that the extensive use of antibiotics in humans as well as their employ for disease prevention and growth promotion in agriculture has led to the appearance of antibiotic-resistant strains [89-92]. Worldly, the evolution of the resistance problem will be aggravated over the decades. Particularly, with the appearance of multi-drug-resistant (MDR) *S. aureus*, principally methicillin resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA), leading to animal and human infections, has become an emergent public health concern [93]. The first emergence of *S. aureus* strains that were resistant to methicillin was identified in the United Kingdom in 1961, soon after the introduction of methicillin antibiotic in medical practice in order to treat infections caused by penicillin resistant *S. aureus* [94-97]. In humans, levels of mortality caused only by multidrug-resistant bacterial infection in European Union and the Unites States were 25,000 and 63,000 patients per year, respectively [98]. According to Frana *et al.* [99], around of 1.5% of the population (~4.1 million persons) is colonized with MRSA leading to at least 94,000 invasive

infections and over 18,000 deaths annually only in the United States. In France, multidrug-resistant bacterial infections cause more than 12,000 deaths each year [100] and 700,000 worldwide [101]. By 2050, without joint international action, antibiotic resistance could become one of the leading causes of mortality worldwide, causing up to 10 million deaths each year [101]. It is in this context that the World Health Organization (WHO) has identified antibiotic resistance as one of the most serious threats to global public health [102]. In addition to death and disability, antimicrobial resistance has significant economic costs. The World Bank estimates that antimicrobial resistance could result in US\$ 1 trillion additional healthcare costs by 2050, and US\$ 1 trillion to US\$ 3.4 trillion gross domestic product (GDP) losses per year by 2030 [103,104]. MRSA has appeared as a most important causative agent of health care-associated (HA) and community-associated (CA) infections [105]. More recently, the spread to public health presented new strains entitled livestock-associated methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (LA-MRSA). The frequent isolation of LA-MRSA has been showed by farmers, veterinarians, and farm workers' family members [106]. In this regards, Aqib *et al.* [84] described that a clonal complex 398 representative of livestock-associated methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) has proven the ability of colonization and serious health consequences in humans who are in close contact with animals. MRSA strains have acquired a gene called *mecA* (this gene codes for a penicillin binding protein, PBP2a, which interferes with the effects of beta lactam antibiotics on cell walls) that makes them resistant to nearly all Beta-lactam antibiotics including semi-synthetic penicillins such as methicillin, oxacillin, or cloxacillin (Notable exceptions to this rule are the latest generation of cephalosporin Beta-lactams, for example, ceftaroline and ceftobiprole). Resistance to other antibiotics is also common, especially in hospital-associated MRSA [107]. However, *mecC*-bearing MRSA is a new resistance gene type of MRSA first recognized in 2011. Many of these organisms have been recovered from animals, particularly dairy cattle, but they can also infect and colonize humans. Therefore, *mecC* (formerly *mecALGA251*) is also a Beta-lactams resistance gene, and is less well understood than *mecA* gene [107]. Similar to *mecA*, *mecC* gene is carried on SCCmec. This new gene codes for a different version of PBP2a, which is also thought to interfere with the effects of Beta-lactams drugs on cell walls. Nevertheless, a recent paper suggests that *mecC* encoded PBP2a may mediate resistance to some Beta-lactams antibiotics, but not others. This could raise the possibility of treatment with some drugs that are ineffective against *mecA* bearing MRSA [107]. Nowadays, the MRSA strains are known as “a superbug” and they represent a major problem in most medical institutions because it is creating life-threatening situations [108]. Moreover, the manifestation of mutated strains of MRSA is the vancomycin resistant *S. aureus* (VRSA) which has added danger to health care communities. In the recent years, VRSA is really became one of the greatest threats-mankind faces because the antibiotic, vancomycin, is the last available alternative used for treating staphylococcal infections [108]. New resistance mechanisms are appearing and spreading around the world, compromising now our ability to treat common infectious diseases. For a growing number of infections, such as mastitis, pneumonia, tuberculosis, sepsis and gonorrhea, and food-borne illnesses, treatment becomes more difficult, if not impossible, because of the loss of antibiotic efficacy. Now, what is more dangerous remains the progressive evolution of increased resistance within pathogenic strains that has been almost noted against all kinds of available antimicrobials compounds and no introduction in parallel of any new drugs has invited the use of newer drug combinations [84]. The use of combined antibiotics in medicine for treating many infections caused by resistance pathogenic bacteria has considered as one of the important strategies followed in recent years in order to stop resistance phenomenon and skip, therefore, this challenge implicated by these pathogenic microorganisms. Unfortunately, this strategy remains a temporary solution for many years because of the dramatically emergence of increased resistance that has been seriously threatening again many human and animal live

around the world. For example, combination of cefaroxil from cephalosporins and amoxicillin from penicillins group showed synergistic effects against 80% of resistant isolates [84]. During recent decades, Estonia was among countries where only antibiotics with broad spectrum have been used for the treatment of clinical mastitis disease [82]. For example, in the years ranging from 2006 to 2009, 15 diverse combinations of antibiotics were on hand for use in 18 intra mammary preparations that were authorized by the Estonian State Medical Agency [109].

In the literature reports, the pathogenic resistance bacteria, particularly *S. aureus*, have nowadays developed and acquired several mechanisms allowing them to avoid efficacy of antimicrobials [2,56]. For example, many genes such as *blaZ*, *mec*, *erm*, *aac/aph*, *tet*, *vga* and *van* are among the prevalent resistance genes noted to play a role in *S. aureus* resistance encoded for several antibiotics such as Beta-lactams, Macrolides, Aminoglycosides, Tetracyclines and Glycopeptides families [2,56,92,95,110-119]. The majority of *S. aureus* strains are now becoming multidrugs-resistance because of acquisition of several resistance genes encoding for almost of antimicrobials agents [2,56]. Bacteria employ horizontal gene transfer from resistant to sensitive strains. Moreover, the development of resistance phenomenon to antimicrobial agents has been observed for a range of these described drugs above in addition to Fluoroquinolones [2,56, 120]. As an example of resistance mechanisms encoded by genes, the inactivation of Beta-lactam antibacterial is effected by bacterial produced enzymes called Beta-lactamases (such as penicillinases, cephalosporinases, carbapenemases, cephamycinases, and so on). Concerning how Beta-lactam drugs work; according to Bugg *et al.* [121], Beta-lactam family acts as a false molecule for D-alanyl-D-alanyl transpeptidases, which result in inhibition of transpeptidation reaction and peptidoglycan synthesis. After that, autolytic enzyme inhibitors get inactivated, which activates the lytic enzyme, in that way resulting in division of bacteria provided that the environment is isotonic. Some other antibiotics such as vancomycin, novobiocin, bacitracin, teicoplanin and ristocetin must be subjected at early stages, which impede early phases of the peptidoglycan synthesis.

In countries where they are dispensed without a prescription for humans or animals, the problem of the emergence and spread of resistance is even worse. Similarly, in countries lacking standardized treatment guidelines, antibiotics are over-prescribed by health workers and veterinarians and over-consumed by the general public. If we do not take emergency measures, we will soon enter a post antibiotic era in which common infections and small wounds will again be fatal. According to Aqib *et al.* [84], the phenomenon of resistance to antibiotics drugs leads to treatment failure against infections mastitis caused by *S. aureus*, so the vaccine development against mastitis stays an exigent to prevent new infections by *S. aureus* for commercial dairy farms. Anti-*Staphylococcus aureus* vaccines give different results, depending on the type of vaccine, the adjuvant used, and some other factors involved, adding the authors. The use of veterinary drugs remains imperative and play a major role in the control of diseases in cattle populations; a good management and preventive practices in the herds can help the reduction of disease expression and consequently the need to resort to drugs that should be done wisely [2,56]. To be sure, agents must be chosen according to their effectiveness to a type of bacteria which can be evaluated by means of an antimicrobial susceptibility testing [2,56]. Because of paucity existence of data on the molecular characterization of *S. aureus* in most countries, better understanding of *S. aureus* antibiotic susceptibility profiles and molecular characterization of genes causing resistance are of paramount importance for initiating effective control measures and reducing staphylococcal infections [2,56,120,122].

Since penicillin became widely available in the 1940s [123,124], antibiotics have played an indispensable role in reducing morbidity and mortality from both common ailments, such as staphylococcal and streptococcal infections, and life-threatening conditions, like sepsis. Nowadays, scientists have warned that the world, in few coming years, will return to a pre-antibiotic age plagued by life-threatening microbial infections on the basis of a recent antibiotic

resistance gene database that lists the existence of more than 20,000 antibiotic-resistant genes of 400 types, predicted from available genome sequences [98]. As a consequence of this new challenge, the discovery of novel antimicrobial agents to which microbes cannot develop resistance easily is one of the major medical concerns of the 21st century [37].

In conclusion of this review, it is clear that the resistance phenomenon to antibiotics remains an imminent threat to the effective treatment of bacterial infections, and alternative antibiotic strategies, in this regards, are urgently mandatory. The golden age of antibiotics is coming to an end, and the development of new therapeutic agents to combat infections caused by pathogenic resistant bacteria should be prioritized.

In memoriam:

This review is dedicated to the soul of my **Professor Mohamed Najimi**.

Conflicts of Interest: The author declare no conflicts of interest.

Transparency declarations: None to declare.

REFERENCE

- [1] Wendlandt S, Shen J, Kadlec K et al., 2015. Multidrug resistance genes in staphylococci from animals that confer resistance to critically and highly important antimicrobial agents in human medicine. *Trends in Microbiology* 23:1. Doi.org/10.1016/j.tim.2014.10.002
- [2] Hnini R, Silva E, Pinho L et al., 2024. Beta-lactam antimicrobials activity and the diversity of bla_Z gene in *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates from bovine mastitis in the northwest of Portugal. *Revista Brasileira de Zootecnia* 53:e20230024. <https://doi.org/10.37496/rbz5320230024>
- [3] Knobler SL, Lemon SM, Najafi M et al., 2003. The Resistance Phenomenon in Microbes and Infectious Disease Vectors: Implications for Human Health and Strategies for Containment: Workshop Summary. Institute of Medicine (US) Forum on Emerging Infections; Washington (DC): National Academies Press (US).
- [4] Julian Davies and Dorothy Davies. Origins and Evolution of Antibiotic Resistance. *Microbiology and molecular biology reviews*, Sept. 2010, p. 417–433 Vol. 74, No. 3 1092-2172/10/\$12.00 doi:10.1128/MMBR.00016-10
- [5] Stacey LK nobler, LemonSL, Najafi M et al., 2003. The Resistance Phenomenon in Microbes and Infectious Disease Vectors: Implications for Human Health and Strategies for Containment -- Workshop Summary. ISBN: 0 309-50746-4, 336 pages, 6 x 9, This PDF is available from the National Academies Press at: <http://www.nap.edu/catalog/10651.html>
- [6] Chen X, Koumoutsi A, Scholz R et al., 2009. Genome analysis of *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* FZB42 reveals its potential for biocontrol of plant pathogens. *J Biotechnol* 140:27-37.
- [7] Sumi CD, Yang BW, Yeo I-C, 2014. Antimicrobial peptides of the genus *Bacillus*: a new era for antibiotics. *Can J Microbiol* 61:93-103.
- [8] Demain AL, 2014. Importance of microbial natural products and the need to revitalize their discovery. *J Ind Microbiol Biotechnol* 41:185-201.
- [9] Dasenaki ME, Thomaidis NS, 2017. Chapter 18 - Meat Safety: II Residues and Contaminants. *Lawrie's Meat Science (Eight Edition)*. Woodhead Publishing Series in Food Science, Technology and Nutrition. Pages553-583. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-100694-8.00018-2>

- [10] Pitkala A, Salmikivi L, Bredbacka P et al., 2007. Comparison of tests for detection of beta-lactamase-producing staphylococci. *J Clin Microbiol* 45: 2031-2033.
- [11] Lara FJ, del Olmo-Iruela M, Cruces-Blanco C, 2012. Advances in the determination of b-lactam antibiotics by liquid chromatography. *Trends in Analytical Chemistry* 38:52-66.
- [12] Schatz A, Bugle E, Waksman SA, 1944. Streptomycin, a Substance Exhibiting Antibiotic Activity Against Gram Positive and Gram Negative Bacteria. *Proceedings of the Society for Experimental Biology and Medicine*. Society for Experimental Biology and Medicine (New York, N.Y.) 55:66-69. Antibiotics by liquid chromatography. *Trends in Analytical Chemistry* 38:52-66.
- [13] Walsh C, 2003. Antibiotics: actions, origins, resistance. ASM Press 2003.
- [14] McGlinchey TA, Rafter PA, Regan F et al., 2008. A review of analytical methods for the determination of aminoglycoside and macrolide residues in food matrices. *Analytic Chimica Acta* 624:1-15.
- [15] Lewis K, 2013. Platforms for antibiotic discovery. *Nat. Rev. Drug Discov* 12:371-387. doi: 10.1038/nrd3975
- [17] Roberts MC, 2003. Tetracycline therapy: Update. *Clin Infect Dis* 36:462-467. Doi.org/10.1086/367622
- [18] Iannelli F, Santoro F, Santagati M et al., 2018. Type M Resistance to Macrolides is Due to a Two-Gene Efflux Transport System of the ATP-Binding Cassette (ABC) Superfamily. *Front. Microbiol* 9:1670. doi:10.3389/fmicb.2018.01670
- [19] Golkar T, Zielinski M, Berghuis AM, 2018. Look and Outlook on Enzyme-Mediated Macrolide Resistance. *Front. Microbiol* 9:1942. doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2018.01942
- [20] Bryskier A, 2000. Ketolides—telithromycin, an example of a new class of antibacterial agents. *Clin. Microbiol. Infect* 6:661-669. doi: 10.1046/j.1469-0691.2000.00185.x
- [21] MacLaughlin EJ, Saseen JJ, Malone DC, 2000. Costs of b-lactam allergies: selection and costs of antibiotics for patients with a reported {beta}-lactam allergy. *Arch. Fam. Med* 9:722-726. doi: 10.1001/archfami. 9.8.722
- [22] Andrew CP, Peter JS, Kalinka K et al., 2018. The evolution of substrate discrimination in macrolide antibiotic resistance enzymes. *Nature Communications* 9:112. DOI: 10.1038/s41467-017-02680-0
- [23] Saribas Z, Tunckanat F, Pinar A, 2006. Prevalence of erm genes encoding macrolide lincosamide streptogramin (MLS) resistance among clinical isolates of *Staphylococcus aureus* in a Turkish university hospital. *Clin Microbiol Infect* 12:797-9. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-0691.2006.01486>.
- [24] Bozdogan B, Appelbaum PC, 2004. Macrolide resistance in streptococci and Haemophilus influenzae. *Clinics in Laboratory Medicine* 24:455-475. DOI: 10.1016/j.cll.2004.03.006
- [25] Schlünzen F, Zarivach R, Harms J et al., 2001. Structural basis for the interaction of antibiotics with the peptidyl transferase centre in eubacteria. *Nature* 413:814-821. DOI: 10.1038/35101544
- [26] Franklin TJ, Snow GA, 1975. *Biochemistry of Antimicrobial Agents*. 2nd ed. New York: John Wiley; 1975.
- [27] Brisson-Noël A, Trieu-Cuot P, Courvalin P, 1988. Mechanism of action of spiramycin and other macrolides. *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy* 22:13-23.
- [28] Petinaki E, Papagiannitsis C, 2018. Resistance of Staphylococci to Macrolides Lincosamides-Streptogramins B (MLS_B): Epidemiology and Mechanisms of Resistance. Department of Microbiology, School of Medicine, University of Thessaly, Larissa, Greece. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.75192>
- [29] Chopra I, Roberts, 2001. Tetracycline Antibiotics: Mode of Action, Applications, Molecular Biology, and Epidemiology of Bacterial Resistance. *Microbiology and molecular biology reviews* 65:232-260. DOI: 10.1128/MMBR.65.2.232-260.2001

- [31] Ehrlich J, Bartz QR, Smith et al., 1947. Chloromycetin, a new antibiotic from a soil actinomycete. *Science* 106:417.
- [32] Ehrlich, J, Gottlieb D, Burkholder et al., 1948. *Streptomyces venezuelae* n. sp. the source of Chloromycetin. *J. Bact* 56,467.
- [33] Gruhzit M, Fiskén RA, Reutner TF et al., 1949. Chloramphenicol (chloromycetin), an antibiotic. pharmacological and pathological studies in animals. *J Clin Invest* 28:943-952. <https://doi.org/10.1172/JCI102184>.
- [34] McGhee CN, Anastas CN, 1996. Widespread ocular use of topical chloramphenicol: is there justifiable concern regarding idiosyncratic aplastic anaemia? *Br. J. Ophthalmol* 80:182-184.
- [35] Erel E, Platt AJ, Ramakrishnan V, 1999. Chloramphenicol use in plastic surgery. *Br. J. Plast. Surg* 52:326-327.
- [36] Controulis J, Rebstock MC, Crooks HM, 1949. Chloramphenicol (Chloromycetin). Synthesis. Read before Am. Chem. Soc., San Francisco, Calif., March 27.
- [37] Das B, Patra S, 2017. Antimicrobials: Meeting the Challenges of Antibiotic Resistance Through Nanotechnology. *Nanostructures for Antimicrobial Therapy* *Micro and Nano Technologies* 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-46152-8.00001-9>
- [38] Fookes C, 2018. Sulfonamides . *BPharm*.
- [39] Scholar E, 2017. Sulfonamides. *xPharm: The Comprehensive Pharmacology Reference*.
- [40] Sharma S, Anand N, 1997. Approaches to Design and Synthesis of Antiparasitic Drugs. *Pharmacochemistry Library*.
- [41] Vass M, Hruska K, Franek M, 2008. Nitrofurantoin antibiotics: a review on the application, prohibition and residual analysis. *Veterinari Medicina* 53:469-500.
- [42] EMA, 2018. Fluoroquinolone and quinolone antibiotics: PRAC recommends new restrictions on use following review of disabling and potentially long-lasting side effects. *EMA/668915/2018*
- [43] Novak R, Shlaes DM, 2010. The pleuromutilin antibiotics: a new class for human use. *Curr Opin Investig Drugs* 11:182-191.
- [44] Paukner S and Riedl R, 2017. Pleuromutilins: Potent Drugs for Resistant Bugs—Mode of Action and Resistance. *Cold Spring Harb Perspect Med* 7:pii:a027110. [doi:10.1101/cshperspect.a027110](https://doi.org/10.1101/cshperspect.a027110).
- [35] Prescott JF, 2013. Sulfonamides, Diaminopyrimidines, and Their Combinations. *Antimicrobial Therapy in Veterinary Medicine, Fifth Edition*. Edited by Steeve Giguère, John F. Prescott and Patricia M. Dowling. © 2013 John Wiley & Sons, Inc. Published 2013 by John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- [46] Woodford N and Livermore DM, 2009. Infections caused by Gram-positive bacteria: a review of the global challenge. *Infection* 59:S4-S16.
- [47] Nair N, Biswas R, Gotz G et al., 2014. Impact of *Staphylococcus aureus* on pathogenesis in polymicrobial infections,” *Infection and Immunity* 82:2162-2169.
- [48] Gould IM, 2005. The clinical significance of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Journal of Hospital Infection* 61:277-282.
- [49] Delorme T, Rose S, Senita J et al., 2009. Epidemiology and susceptibilities of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* in Northeastern Ohio. *The American Journal of Clinical Pathology* 132:616-687.
- [50] Klein EY, Sun L, Smith DL et al., 2013. The changing epidemiology of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* in the United States: a national observational study. *The American Journal of Epidemiology* 177:666-674.
- [51] Shen H, Akoda E, Zhang K et al., 2013. Methicillin-resistant *staphylococcus aureus* carriage among students at a historically black university: a case study,” *International Journal of Microbiology* pages 7. ID 979734

- [52] Onal A, 2011. Overview on liquid chromatographic analysis of tetracycline residues in food matrices. *Food Chemistry* 127:197-203.
- [53] Gomes F, Saavedra MJ, Henriques M, 2016. Bovine mastitis disease/pathogenicity: evidence of the potential role of microbial biofilms. *Pathog Dis* 74:pii: ftw006. doi: 10.1093/femspd/ftw006. Epub 2016 Jan 14.
- [54] Barkema HW, Schukken YH, Zadoks RN, 2006. Invited review: the role of cow, pathogen, and treatment regimen in the therapeutic success of bovine *Staphylococcus aureus* mastitis. *J. Dairy Sci* 89:1877-1895. Doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302(06)72256-1
- [55] Halasa T, Huijps K, Osteras O et al., 2007. Economic effects of bovine mastitis and mastitis management: A review. *Vet Quat* 29:18-31.
- [56] Hnini R, Silva E, Pinho L et al., 2023. Phenotypic characterization and resistance genes detection of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolated from bovine mastitis in the Northwest of Portugal. *Acta Veterinaria Eurasia*, 49(3), 127-136.
- [57] Watts JL, 1988. Etiological agents of bovine mastitis. *Vet Microbiol* 16:41-66. Doi.org/10.1016/0378-1135(88)90126-5
- [58] Bradley AJ, 2002. Bovine mastitis: an evolving disease. *Veterinary Journal* 164:116-128. Doi.org/10.1053/tvjl.2002.0724
- [59] Barkema HW, Green MJ, Bradley et al., 2009. Invited review: the role of contagious disease in udder health. *J. Dairy Sci* 92:4717-4729. Doi.org/10.3168/jds.2009-2347
- [60] Awale MM, Dudhatra GB, Avinash K et al., 2012. Bovine mastitis: a threat to economy.
- [61] Kerro DO, Van Dijk JE, Nederbragt H, 2002. Factors involved in the early pathogenesis of bovine *Staphylococcus aureus* mastitis with emphasis on bacterial adhesion and invasion. *Vet Q* 24:181-198.
- [62] Cramton SE, Gerke C, Schnell NF et al., 1999. The intracellular adhesion (ica) locus is present in *Staphylococcus aureus* and is required for biofilm formation. *Infect Immun* 67:5427-5433.
- [63] Hiramatsu K, Cui L, Kuroda M et al., 2001. The emergence and evolution of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Trends Microbiol* 9:486-493. Doi.org/10.1016/S0966-842X(01)02175-8
- [64] Rega M, Andriani L, Poeta A et al., 2023. The pork food chain as a route of transmission of antimicrobial resistant *Escherichia coli*: a farm-to-fork perspective. *Antibiotics (Basel)*. 12(2):376.
- [65] Antimicrobial Resistance Collaborators, 2023. The burden of antimicrobial resistance in the Americas in 2019: a cross-country systematic analysis. *Lancet Reg Health Am* 25:100561.
- [66] Antimicrobial Resistance Collaborators, 2022. Global burden of bacterial antimicrobial resistance in 2019: a systematic analysis. *Lancet* 399(10325):629-55.
- [67] Allel K, Day L, Hamilton A et al., 2023. Global antimicrobial-resistance drivers: an ecological country-level study at the human-animal interface. *Lancet Planet Health* 7(4):e291-303.
- [68] Fujita AW, Werner K, Jacob JT et al., 2022. Antimicrobial resistance through the lens of one health in Ethiopia: a review of the literature among humans, animals, and the environment. *Int J Infect Dis* 119:120-9.
- [69] Fonseca M, Heider LC, Stryhn H et al., 2023. Intramammary and systemic use of antimicrobials and their association with resistance in generic *Escherichia coli* recovered from fecal samples from Canadian dairy herds: a cross-sectional study. *Prev Vet Med* 216:105948
- [70] Qi Z, Zinan J, Ting L et al., 2023. Current status and trends in antimicrobial use in food animals in China, 2018-2020. Zhao et al. *One Health Advances* 1:29. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s44280-023-00029-5>
- [71] Ibrahim M, Ahmad F, Yaqub B et al., 2020. Antibiotics and Antimicrobial Resistance Genes in the Environment, Chapter 4 - Current trends of antimicrobials used in food animals

- and aquaculture. In *Advances in Environmental Pollution Research series*, Volume 1, Pages 39-69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-818882-8.00004-8>.
- [72] Zwald AG, Ruegg PL, Kaneene JB et al., 2004. Management practices and reported antimicrobial usage on conventional and organic dairy farms. *J Dairy Sci* 87:191-201. [Doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302\(04\)73158-6](https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302(04)73158-6)
- [73] Rajala-Schultz PJ, Smith KL, Hogan JS et al., 2004. Antimicrobial susceptibility of mastitis pathogens from first lactation and older cows. *Vet. Microbiol* 102:33-42. [Doi.org/10.1016/j.vetmic.2004.04.010](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetmic.2004.04.010)
- [74] Mitchell JM, Griffiths MW, McEwen SA et al., 1998. Antimicrobial drug residues in milk and meat: causes, concerns, prevalence, regulations, tests, and test performance. *J. Food Prot* 61:742-756.
- [75] O'Reilly T, Kunz S, Sande E et al., 1992. Relationship between antibiotic concentration in bone and efficacy of treatment of staphylococcal osteomyelitis in rats: azithromycin compared with clindamycin and rifampin. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 36:2693-2697.
- [76] Almeida RA, Matthews KR, Cifrian E et al., 1996. *Staphylococcus aureus* invasion of bovine mammary epithelial cells. *Journal of Dairy Science* 79:1021-1026.
- [77] Moreillon P, Que YA, Glauser MP. 2005. *Staphylococcus aureus*, p. 2321-2351. In: G. E. Mandell, J. E. Bennett, and R. Dolin (eds.), *Principles and practice of infectious diseases*. Elsevier, Philadelphia, PA.
- [78] Sompolinsky D, Samra Z, Karakawa WW et al., 1985. Encapsulation and capsular types in isolates of *Staphylococcus aureus* from different sources and relationship to phage types. *J Clin Microbiol* 22:828-834.
- [79] Luong T, Sau S, Gomez M et al., 2002. Regulation of *Staphylococcus aureus* Capsular Polysaccharide Expression by agrA. *Infection and Immunity* 70:444-450. DOI: 10.1128/IAI.70.2.444-450.2002
- [80] Cocchiari JL, Gomez MI, Risley A et al., 2006. Molecular characterization of the capsule locus from non-typeable *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Mol. Microbiol* 59:948-960.
- [81] Bera A, Biswas R, Herbert S et al., 2006. The presence of peptidoglycan O-acetyltransferase in various staphylococcal species correlates with lysozyme resistance and pathogenicity. *Infect. Immun* 74:4598-4604
- [82] Kalmus P, Aasmäe B, Kärssin A et al., 2011. Udder pathogens and their resistance to antimicrobial agents in dairy cows in Estonia. *Acta Vet Scand* 53:54.
- [83] Erskine RJ, Walker RD, Bolin CA et al., 2001. Trends in antibacterial susceptibility of mastitis pathogens during a seven-year period. *J Dairy Sci* 85:1111-1118.
- [84] Aqib AI, Ijaz M, Farooqi SH, 2019. Dairy *Staphylococcus aureus*: Epidemiology, Drug Susceptibilities, Drug Modulation, and Preventive Measures. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.74552>
- [86] Pitkala A, Haveri H, Pyörala S et al., 2004. Bovine mastitis in Finland 2001—Prevalence, distribution of bacteria, and antimicrobial resistance. *J Dairy Sci* 87: 2433-2441.
- [87] Lewies A, Du Plessis LH, Wentzel JF, 2019. Antimicrobial Peptides: the Achilles' Heel of Antibiotic Resistance?. *Probiotics Antimicrob Proteins* 11:370-381. doi:10.1007/s12602-018-9465-0.
- [88] Netsvyetayeva I, Fraczek M, Piskorska K et al., 2014. *Staphylococcus aureus* nasal carriage in Ukraine: Antibacterial resistance and virulence factor encoding genes. *BMC Infectious Diseases* 14:128. doi:10.1186/1471-2334-14-128
- [89] Hamer DH, Gill CJ, 2002. From the farm to the kitchen table: The negative impact of antimicrobial use in animals on humans. *Nutrition Reviews* 60:261-264. doi:10.1301/002966402320289395

- [90] Martínez JL and Baquerom F, 2002. Interactions among strategies associated with bacterial infection: Pathogenicity, epidemicity, and antibiotic resistance. *Clinical Microbiology Reviews* 15:647-679. doi:10.1128/CMR.15.4.647-679.2002
- [91] Phillips I, Casewell M, Cox T et al., 2004. Does the use of antibiotics in food animals pose a risk to human health? A critical review of published data. *The Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy* 53:28-52. doi:10.1093/jac/dkg483
- [92] Ma Y, Zhao Y, Tang J et al., 2017. Antimicrobial susceptibility and presence of resistance & enterotoxins/enterotoxin-like genes in *Staphylococcus aureus* from food. *Antimicrobial susceptibility and presence of resistance & enterotoxins/enterotoxin-like genes in Staphylococcus aureus from food, CyTA - Journal of Food* 16:76-84. DOI: 10.1080/19476337.2017.1340341
- [93] Li L, Zhou L, Wang L et al., 2015. Characterization of methicillin-resistant and -susceptible staphylococcal isolates from bovine milk in northwestern China. *PLoS ONE* 10:e0116699. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0116699
- [94] Jevons MP, 1961. Celbenin[™]-resistant staphylococci. *BMJ* 1:124-125.
- [95] DeLeo FR and Chambers HF, 2009. Reemergence of antibiotic-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* in the genomics era. *J. Clin. Investig* 119:2464-2474.
- [96] Kejela T and Bacha K, 2013. Prevalence and antibiotic susceptibility pattern of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) among primary school children and prisoners in Jimma Town, Southwest Ethiopia. *Annals of Clinical Microbiology and Antimicrobials* 12:11. DOI:10.1186/1476-0711-12-11
- [97] Simonetti O, Cirioni O, Orlando F et al., 2011. Effectiveness of antimicrobial photodynamic therapy with a single treatment of RLP068/Cl in an experimental model of *Staphylococcus aureus* wound infection. *The British Journal of Dermatology* 164:987-995. DOI:10.1111/j.1365-2133.2011.10232.x
- [98] Liu C, Graber CJ, Karr M et al., 2008. A population-based study of the incidence and molecular epidemiology of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* disease in San Francisco, 2004–2005. *Clin Infect Dis* 46:1637-1646.
- [99] Frana TS, Beahm AR, Hanson BM et al., 2013. Isolation and characterization of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* from pork farms and visiting veterinary students. *PLoS One*, 8, e53738. doi:10.1371/journal.
- [100] Colomb-Cotin M, Lacoste J, Brun-Buisson C et al., 2012. Estimating the morbidity and mortality associated with infections due to multidrug-resistant bacteria (MDRB), France. *Antimicrob Resist Infect Control* 2016;5:56.
- [101] Review on antimicrobial resistance, 2016. Tackling drug-resistant infections globally: Final report and recommendations. 84 p. [https://amr-review.org/sites/default/files/160525_Final %20paper_with%20cover.pdf](https://amr-review.org/sites/default/files/160525_Final%20paper_with%20cover.pdf)
- [102] Chabaud A, Jouzeau A, Dugravot L et al., 2020. Consommation d'antibiotiques et résistances bactériennes en établissement de santé. Données spares, Antibiorésistance en France en 2021 : une menace sous surveillance, *BEH* 18-19.
- [103] Antimicrobial Resistance Collaborators (AMRC), (2022). Global burden of bacterial antimicrobial resistance in 2019: a systematic analysis. *The Lancet*; 399(10325): P629-655. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(21\)02724-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(21)02724-0)
- [104] WHO, 2023. Antimicrobial resistance. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/antimicrobial-resistance> (accessed 11.05.2025)
- [105] Klein E, Smith DL, Laxminarayan R, 2007. Hospitalizations and deaths caused by methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*, United States, 1999–2005. *Emerg Infect Dis* 13:1840-1846.

- [106] Loncaric I, Brunthaler R, Spersger J, 2013. Suspected goat-to-human transmission of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* sequence type 398. *Journal of Clinical Microbiology* 51:1625-1626.
- [108] Khan Z, Faisal S, Hasnain S, 2010. The continuing threat of Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*—past, present, future. *Journal of Scientific Research* 40:31-34.
- [109] Estonia State Medical Agency (ESMA), 2009. Official annual report. Usage of antimicrobial agents in animals. Estonia 2009.
- [110] Vahaboglu H, Ozturk R, Akbal H et al., 1998. Practical approach for detection and identification of OXA-10-derived ceftazidime-hydrolyzing extended-spectrum beta-lactamases. *Journal of Clinical Microbiology* 36:827-829.
- [111] Lina G, Quaglia A, Reverdy ME et al., 1999. Distribution of genes encoding resistance to macrolides, lincosamides, and streptogramins among staphylococci. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy* 43:1062-1066.
- [112] Martineau F, Picard FJ, Lansac N et al., 2000. Correlation between the resistance genotype determined by multiplex PCR assays and the antibiotic susceptibility patterns of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 44:231-238.
- [113] Strommenger B, Kettlitz C, Werner G et al., 2003. Multiplex PCR assay for simultaneous detection of nine clinically relevant antibiotic resistance genes in *Staphylococcus aureus*. *J Clin Microbiol* 41:4089-4094.
- [114] Choi SM, Kim SH, Kim HJ et al., 2003. Multiplex PCR for the detection of genes encoding aminoglycoside modifying enzymes and methicillin resistance among *Staphylococcus* species. *Journal of Korean Medical Science* 18:631-636. doi:10.3346/jkms.2003.18.5.631
- [115] Feßler A, Scott C, Kadlec K et al., 2010. Characterization of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* ST398 from cases of bovine mastitis. *J Antimicrob Chemother* 65: 619-625.
- [116] Duran N, Ozer B, Duran GG et al., 2012. Antibiotic resistance genes & susceptibility patterns in staphylococci. *Indian Journal of Medical Research*, 135(3), 389–396.
- [117] Tang JN, Zhang R, Chen J et al., 2015. Incidence and characterization of *Staphylococcus aureus* strains isolated from food markets. *Annals of Microbiology* 65:279-286. doi:10.1007/s13213-014-0859-2
- [118] Farid A, Naz I, Ashraf A et al., 2015. Molecular detection of antimicrobial resistance in local isolates of *Staphylococcus epidermidis* from urinary tract infections in Faisalabad region of Pakistan. *EXCLI Journal*, 14:697-705. eCollection2015. 10.17179/excli2015-294
- [119] Pekana A, Green E, 2018. Antimicrobial Resistance Profiles of *Staphylococcus aureus* Isolated from Meat Carcasses and Bovine Milk in Abattoirs and Dairy Farms of the Eastern Cape, South Africa. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 15:2223. Doi:10.3390/ijerph15102223
- [120] Akpaka PE, Kissoon S, Rutherford C et al., 2008. Evaluation of methods and costs for detecting methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates from clinical specimens at regional hospitals in Trinidad and Tobago. *West Indian Med. J* 57:24-27.
- [122] Esan CO, Famurewa O, Lin J et al., 2009. Characterization of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates obtained from health care institutions in Ekiti and Ondo States, South-Western Nigeria. *Afr. J. Microbiol. Res* 3:962-968.
- [123] Gaynes R, 2017. The discovery of Penicillin—New insights after more than 75 years of clinical use. *Emerg. Infect. Dis* 23, 849–853.
- [124] Klein EY, Impalli I, Poleon S, et al., 2024. Global trends in antibiotic consumption during 2016–2023 and future projections through 2030. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.*, 121 (49). <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2411919121>.